

ANALYSIS OF A GFRP STRUCTURAL BOLTED CONNECTION

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials have gained space in civil engineering applications due to the corrosion resistance, low density and attractive mechanical and chemical properties. As an alternative composite material, pultruded glass fiber reinforced polymer (pGFRP), can be used in many structural applications, like telecommunications and cooling towers, footbridges, among others. The main objective of this work was to investigate the behavior of a beam-column bolted connection (double-angle). Two types of connection elements were used: steel angles and GFRP angles. The results showed that the dominant failure mode for the connection using steel angles was caused by bearing, while for GFRP angles was shear out.

KEYWORDS

Pultruded GFRP, bolted connection, connection failure modes

INTRODUCTION

Composites materials gained attention through the decades in a variety of engineering applications such as aircraft, trains and civil construction (Sharma et al., 2018). In civil engineering, the fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) is extensively used due the mechanical properties and the resistance against aggressive environments conditions (Gonabadi et al., 2022), resulting in unique buildings as the Pontresina bridge (Keller et al., 2007), made entirely by glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP). Moreover, FRP's materials are commonly recommended to reinforce concrete columns, beams (Dai et al., 2022) and to strengthen and repair load-bearing structural members (Bank, 2006).

The structural analysis includes the designs of beams, columns, slabs as well as the connections, whose main function is to transfer the forces between structural elements. For this reason, connections are considered the critical part of the structure (Mallick, 2007), which allows the viability or unfeasibility of a design. When it comes to composite materials, the scenario is even more delicate and needs caution due to the orthotropic properties and its influence in determining the load path (Bank, 2006). Furthermore, the anisotropic and non-homogeneous directional properties, allied with the inability in redistributing loads to avoid local stress concentrations makes it more difficult to work with GFRP pultruded shapes (Girão Coelho & Mottram, 2015), especially in bolted connections.

Nowadays, recent studies such as (Jiang et al., 2021), (Tran et al., 2022) and (Girão Coelho & Mottram, 2015) showed the behavior of different types of GFRP connections on account of shear and tensile forces by studying the influence of factors such as the number of bolts, the geometry and the type of load on determining the connection strength.

The aim of this paper was to evaluate a shear bolted connection from a frame of an industrial mezzanine made of GFRP elements, on a service temperature up to 40°C, based on the Brazilian standard for design of GFRP structures, under development (ABNT, 2023). Two cases were analyzed: the first, a connection design using pGFRP for all elements and the second one the pGFRP angles were replaced by steel angles. It is worth noting that stainless steel bolts were used for both types of connections. The connection's final resistance and the failure modes in each scenario will be presented and further discussions comparing the results were made.

METHODOLOGY

Structure elements and materials

The frame structure analysed is present in Figure 1a. For columns were chosen WF 304 x 19 kg/m and for the beam the profile I 350 x 14 kg/m. The beam is connected to the flange's columns by double angles (ASTM A36 and pGFRP) using ASTM A325 steel bolts, Figure 1b.

For the two types of connections, all the bolts, nuts and washers are made of stainless steel and have nominal dimensions of 15.9 mm, 15.9 mm and 31.8 mm, respectively.

The nominal dimensions of the structural elements are presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

Figure 1: GFRP frame and connection

Table 1: Nominal dimensions of the frame elements

GFRP Shapes	t_w (mm)	d (mm)	t_f (mm)	b (mm)
Column	12.70	304.80	12.70	304.80
Beam	12.00	350.00	15.00	112.00

Table 2: Nominal dimensions of the connection's elements

Connection Elements	t (mm)	h (mm)	w (mm)	Material
	6.35	190.80	120.00	ASTM A36
	6.35	190.80	120.00	GFRP

Mechanical Properties

Table 3 and Table 4 show the mechanical properties of the GFRP material and steel elements, respectively. The properties of GFRP material are the minimum values accepted by Brazilian pre-standard for pultruded profiles (ABNT, 2023).

Table 3 - Mechanical properties of GFRP material

Longitudinal Tensile Strength – (MPa)	Transverse Tensile Strength – (MPa)	In plane shear strength – (MPa)	Longitudinal pin-bearing strength – (MPa)	Transverse pin-bearing strength – (MPa)	Through the Thickness strength – (MPa)
240	50	30	150	70	25

Table 4 - Mechanical properties of steel elements

Connection Element	Ultimate Strength (f_u) - MPa	Yield Strength (f_y) - MPa	Steel
Angle	400	250	ASTM A36
Bolts	825	635	ASTM A325

Design

Structural connections can be classified according to the amount of transferred moment between the elements (Fakury et al., 2016) and the type of joining (Egorov et al., 2022). The applicability of each depends on the load, project characteristics and materials. The focus of this work is on a beam-column flexible bolted connection, very common in framing structures (Bank, 2006).

The shear force applied in the connection, resulting from distributed load along and perpendicular to the beam axis, was considered at the edge of the columns flange, as shown in Figure 2b.

To properly define the geometry, to calculate the strength and to identify the failure modes of the connection, it is necessary to define what is a row and a line of bolts. A row of bolts is defined as being the alignment of bolts in the perpendicular direction of the load whereas a line of bolts is the alignment of bolts in the parallel direction of the load.

Thus, the distances between bolts from the same row (g), hole and edge (e_1 and e_2) and rows of bolts (s) are present in Table 5, and the final connection geometry is shown in Figure 2.

Table 5: Connection geometry parameters (in mm)

Distances	e_1	e_2	s	g
Minimum	31.80	23.85	63.60	63.60
Adopted	31.80	28.53	63.60	63.60

In each connection 12 bolts are being used on the flange of the column, while 6 bolts are being used in the web of the beam. Since the connection has two lines of bolts, the eccentricity caused by the loading on the connection must be considered (Fakury et al., 2016), (Boracchini, 2018). The positioning of the concentrated equivalent load is shown in Figure 2b. Also, according to (Boracchini, 2018), it is possible to adopt the load application point at infinite locations, since the equilibrium is respected and the joint possesses ductility to enter the plastic state. The eccentricities e' and e'' are shown on Figure 2.

All the calculations and the geometric requirements of the connection were based on the Brazilian pre-standard for design of GFRP structures (ABNT, 2023).

Figure 2: Detailing of the connection design (dimensions in mm)

Failure Modes

Pultruded shapes made of composite materials have specific failure modes responsible for the connection's viability. The following failure modes were evaluated: Bolt strength (R_{bt}); Through the thickness strength (R_{tt}); Bearing strength (R_{br}); Net tension strength (R_{nt}); Shear out strength (R_{sh}); Cleavage strength (R_{cl}); Block shear (R_{bs}). However, due the nature of the loading and type of connection, Cleavage and Net tension strengths were disregarded. The verification of all modes

was done for the beam web, column flange and angles since the resistances found can be different depending on the geometry, number of bolts, and mechanical properties.

Bolt Strength (R_{bt})

The bolt strength is given by following Equation 1:

$$R_{bt} = \alpha_b R_{np} A_b \tag{Eq. 1}$$

where R_{np} is the nominal bolt strength in MPa, A_b is the cross-sectional area of the bolt and α_b is the failure mode reduction coefficient equal to 0.75.

The value obtained by Equation 1 refers to the resistant force provided by a single bolt. Each one is subjected exclusively to a shear loading. As the only bolts allowed by the Brazilian pre-standard for pultruded profiles (ABNT, 2023) are those made of ASTM A307, A325 and A490 type steel, the bolts will not be critical elements on the connection in view of the high values of the steel mechanical properties. However, aggressive environments require greater care with the treatment of the bolts to inhibit corrosive agents.

Bearing strength (R_{br})

Pin bearing failure (Figure 3) can occur in the longitudinal or transverse direction. In both cases, the pin bearing strength is calculated according to Equation 2. Due to eccentricity, it was necessary to calculate the bearing longitudinally and transversally.

Figure 3: Bearing failure

$$R_{br} = \alpha_c t d_p f^{br} \tag{Eq. 2}$$

where t is the thickness of the FRP element, d_p is the nominal bolt diameter, f^{br} is the characteristic pin bearing strength and α_c is the failure mode reduction coefficient equal to 0.8.

For steel elements, the strength was calculated using the Brazilian steel standard ABNT NBR 8800 (2008), which gives the Equation 3.

$$F_{c,Rd} = lower \left\{ \frac{1,2l_f t f_u}{\gamma_{a2}} ; \frac{2,4d_p t f_u}{\gamma_{a2}} \right\} \tag{Eq. 3}$$

where l_f is the shortest distance in the direction of force between the edge of the hole and the edge of the adjacent hole (or end), t is the thickness of the angle, f_u is the ultimate strength of steel, γ_{a2} is the steel reduction coefficient for yielding which is 1.35 and d_p is the bolt diameter.

For both column flange and the beam web, the pin bearing strength was calculated with the material transverse properties. For the connection that used GFRP pultruded angles, the strength was calculated with the longitudinal properties due to the direction of pultrusion in angles.

Shear out Strength (R_{sh})

Shear out failure can happen in two ways: the first one can occur between bolt holes of the same line of bolts (Figure 4a); the second can occur between the outermost hole and the farthest edge of the element from the load point (Figure 4b).

Figure 4: Shear out failures

For beams that have an element perpendicular to the direction of the acting load, the verification between hole and edge can be neglected. Thus, the beam and column were analyzed considering only the shear out between holes of the same bolt line. However, for the angle, both cases were evaluated, and the smaller value was chosen as the critical one. Equation 4 describes the shear out between holes and Equation 5 describes the shear out between hole and edge.

$$R_{sh} = 2\alpha_c((n_f - 1)s)tf_{12} \tag{Eq. 4}$$

$$R_{sh} = 2\alpha_c\left(e_1 - \frac{d_n}{2}\right)tf_{12} \tag{Eq. 5}$$

where d_n is the hole diameter and e_1 is the distance between the hole and the farthest edge in the load direction.

To calculate shear out in steel structures, the Brazilian steel standard ABNT NBR 8800 (2008) was used and the equation can be found below:

$$F_{Rd} = lower \left\{ \frac{0,6A_{gv}f_y}{\gamma_{a1}} ; \frac{0,6A_{nv}f_u}{\gamma_{a2}} \right\} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where A_{nv} is the net area subject to shear, A_{gv} is the gross area subject to shear, f_u is the ultimate strength of steel, f_y is the yield strength of steel, γ_{a2} is the reduction coefficient of steel for rupture that is equal to 1.35, γ_{a1} is the reduction coefficient of steel for yielding and is equal to 1.10.

Block Shear Strength (R_{bs})

In accordance with (Fakury et al., 2016), profiles that do not have a cutout in their geometry do not need to be checked for block shear, Figure 5. However, when considered the angle and made of GFRP, it was necessary to perform the verification using Equation 7. For study purposes, the block shear was also calculated for the column and beam.

Figure 5: Block Shear failure

$$R_{bs} = 0,5\alpha_c(A_{ns}f_{12} + A_{nt}f_{1,t}) \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where A_{ns} is the net area submitted to shear, A_{nt} is the net submitted to tensile, $f_{1,t}$ is the characteristic tensile strength in the longitudinal direction of the FRP material, α_c is the failure mode reduction coefficient, equal to 0.45.

For the steel angles, block shear was calculated using Equation 8, provided by Brazilian steel standard ABNT NBR 8800 (2008).

$$F_{r,Rd} = lower \left\{ \frac{0,6A_{nv}f_u + C_{ts}A_{nt}f_u}{\gamma_{a2}} ; \frac{0,6A_{gv}f_y + C_{ts}A_{nt}f_u}{\gamma_{a2}} \right\} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

where A_{nt} is the net area subjected to tensile stress and C_{ts} is the uniformity coefficient of tensile stress in the net area, which is equal to 1 for shapes and 0.5 for plates.

Through the thickness strength (R_{tt})

The bolts in the column flange will be tensioned due to the acting load. Thus, there will be a tendency for the fibers to detach one from another. The value of R_{tt} was found using Equation 9:

$$R_{tt} = \alpha_b \min \{ 0,5\pi d_w t f_{12} ; 0,4\pi d_w t f_{ILSS} \} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where t is the thickness of the column flange, f_{LSS} is the characteristic shear strength in the through-the-thickness plane, f_{12} is the shear strength of the material in the shear plane, d_w is the outer diameter of the washer, α_b is the failure mode reduction coefficient equal to 0.5.

Angles ($R_{sh, sp}$)

As composite angles are not allowed in the Brazilian pre-standard for pultruded profiles (ABNT, 2023), the verification of this failure mode was done using the Pre-Standard for Load and Resistance Factor Design (LRFD) of Pultruded Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) Structures (ASCE, 2010), provided by Equation 10.

$$R_{sh,sp} = l_{sp} t_{sp} f_{12} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

where t_{sp} is the thickness of the angle and l_{sp} the height of the corner in the loading direction.

Reduction Coefficients

The reduction coefficients are addressed in the standard in order to ensure the proper functioning and safety of the structure made of GFRP, being applied at the end of the determination of the dominant failure mode. The Brazilian pre-standard for design of GFRP structures (ABNT, 2023) considers three parameters: geometry factor (C_Δ), environmental factor (η_e) and the factor due to the combination of loads (λ).

The reduction in the final connection resistance can be influenced by not achieving the minimum distances in the design stage, where in certain cases it is allowed to use values less than the minimums with the onus of having C_Δ reduced. Since all design criteria have been satisfied, $C_\Delta = 1$.

Although GFRP is resistant to aggressive environments, the presence of moisture in the material causes a reduction in the composite's strength (Tefera et al., 2022). Similarly, high temperatures are also a reason for attention due to the existing resin used in the GFRP matrix. For this example, $\eta_e = 0.8$ were considered, which corresponds to structures executed indoors acting at a maximum service temperature of 40°C. The coefficient λ needs to be determined using the Brazilian standard ABNT NBR 8681 (2004) which provides the load combinations to be used. In this work, was adopted $\lambda = 0.8$.

When the bolts are operating in single lap shear, the Brazilian pre-standard for design of GFRP structures (ABNT, 2023) also instructs a 40% reduction on the final connection design resistance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tables 6 and 7 show the results of the strength related to each failure mode for the connections using a steel double angle and GFRP double angles, respectively.

Table 6: Failure modes values with steel double angles

Element	Bolt (kN)	Pin Bearing (kN)	Through the Thickness (kN)	Shear Out (kN)	Block Shear (kN)
Column	214.3	65.79	58.11	71.34	341.7
Beam	214.3	42.72	-	68.71	218.5
Angle	214.3	323.09	-	312.25	484.22

Table 7: Failure modes values with GFRP double angles

Element	Bolt (kN)	Pin Bearing (kN)	Through the Thickness (kN)	Shear Out (kN)	Block Shear (kN)
Column	214.3	65.79	58.11	71.34	341.7
Beam	214.3	42.72	-	68.71	218.5
Angle	214.3	21.58	-	15.8	91.87

Table 8 shows the final connection's resistance, which were calculated applying all the reduction factors on the lower values found in Table 6 and Table 7:

Table 8: Final connection's resistance

Angles	Connection Resistance (kN)	Dominant Failure mode
Steel	16.40	Pin Bearing
GFRP	6.07	Shear Out

The results show that for the original scenario, considering the angle made of steel, the predominant failure mode was the pin bearing that occurs in the web of the beam. As the loading on the beam causes a transverse bearing of the hole, the characteristic strength used is the transverse one, which is 53.3% lower than the longitudinal one. It is still possible to notice that the through thickness is the second most critical failure mode but occurs only with 58.11 kN, which is 36% more than the value found for the bearing failure. Bearing was also the dominant failure mode found by (Jiang et al., 2021). Therefore, the choice of a product with better transverse properties allows it to reach a higher final resistance.

Considering the angles as made of GFRP, there is a decrease in the final value found, a change in the predominant failure mode and in the element that the failure occurs. In this scenario the shear out between the farthest hole and the edge of the angle is the critical mode responsible for the connection failure with a value that corresponds to 3.06% of the shear out value found in the previous scenario. This difference is expected due to the analysis performed considering only the change of the materials adopted, which results in maintaining the low thickness of 6.35mm while reducing the mechanical properties.

CONCLUSION

In accordance with the results, it is understood that the ideal is to work with angles being made of steel. The low resistance of the connection is due to the adoption of GFRP in these elements, resulting in compromising values after the application of the reduction coefficients. Furthermore, it is possible to improve the bearing strength using the same mechanical properties by adding one more row of bolts and make the new connection design compatible considering the minimum distances commented in the design section.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.